

NEW STAGES OF BANKING SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *This article examines the interrelationship between the digital economy and the banking system. In particular, the development of digitalization in the banking system, innovations, financial technologies (FinTech) and Uzbekistan's participation in this process are highlighted. The main goal of the article is to assess the integration opportunities between the digital economy and the banking system and determine its place in the development of the national economy. Also, based on the analysis of the role and importance of the digital economy in the banking system, the article highlights the opportunities and problems arising from the integration of these two areas, and draws conclusions on the prospects for the digitalization process in the case of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *financial technologies (FinTech), banking system, digitalization process, socio-economic process, information and communication technologies (ICT).*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the digital economy is considered a key factor in social and economic development on a global scale. This industry has brought about revolutionary changes in all sectors, from production processes to services, finance and banking. The banking system is at the heart of the digitization process, playing a leading role in providing convenient and secure services to customers.

The current economy is undergoing rapid digitization processes. As a result of globalization and technological innovations, the digital economy is having a significant impact on all sectors of economic activity, including the banking system. The banking system, as the main driver of the digital economy, plays an important role in digitizing not only financial transactions, but also socio-economic processes. The digital economy allows us to increase global competitiveness, while ensuring economic stability and efficiency.

MAIN PART

The digital economy increases production efficiency, develops innovative services and improves the business environment. The banking sector in particular benefits significantly from this process: the ability to provide fast service, reduce costs and expand the customer base.

The digital economy is a form of economy based on the use of the Internet, information and communication technologies (ICT) and digital data. The most important feature of the digital economy is the emergence of data as a new “economic resource”. This term first appeared in the 1990s and has now become an integral part of the global economy. This concept, defined by the American scientist Nicholas Negroponte in 1995, has become a new paradigm of the global economy today.

The digital economy is a new form of economic activity development based on technological innovations, mainly based on the use of digital technologies, the Internet and information systems. The main components of the digital economy include:

1. Data and data analytics: Improving decision-making for businesses and the public sector.
2. Internet and information technology: The critical role of global connectivity and networks.
3. Financial technology (FinTech): Developing payment systems, online trading and investment platforms.
4. Information and communication technology (ICT): Using the Internet and artificial intelligence technologies.
5. Digital platforms: E-commerce, online services and payment systems.
6. Blockchain and digital currencies: Key factors in the transformation of the financial system.

It should also be noted that the coronavirus pandemic has led to an increase in the level of demand for the use of digital services by individuals and legal entities, as well as the state. And the supply of such services, their pricing criteria, speed, quality and efficiency often depend on the development of the digital economy of the state in general and a particular bank in particular, as well as on the speed of adaptation of payment systems to new challenges of our time.

Thus, we see that the COVID-19 pandemic has been able to push modern business to develop and accelerate the implementation of digital technologies that allow the country's economy to "work at arm's length", while ensuring the necessary level of security in the interaction of the seller and buyer of any goods and services, including banking products. The idea of introducing biometric data and digital IDs for both individuals and small and medium-sized enterprises has become very popular lately. During the pandemic, it was necessary to quite competently balance the interests of wider use of digital payments and other financial services with more careful monitoring of increasing cybersecurity risks.

Thus, the key task implemented by the banking system during the pandemic and after it is to adapt to the changed needs of customers and transform its services in accordance with the new realities of the digital economy.

The digital economy increases efficiency, opens up new markets and creates greater convenience for consumers. However, technological developments also raise challenges such as cybersecurity, data privacy and job losses.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Currently, the banking system is enriched with innovations and offers new types of services for customers. The digital economy has become one of the main drivers of the development of the banking system. Today, internet banking, mobile banking, blockchain technologies, electronic wallets, i.e. electronic payments and other digital services have made financial transactions more convenient and faster for customers.

In the case of Uzbekistan, payment systems such as "Humo", "Uzcard", "Click", "Payme" are making a significant contribution to increasing the efficiency of the population's use of financial services and the digitalization of the economy. In particular, the "Humo" system has achieved significant success in automating interbank payments.

Technologies such as data processing algorithms based on artificial intelligence allow for the automation of banking services and the optimization of customer service. For example:

- Automatic determination of a customer's credit rating during the loan application process.

- 24/7 service provision through chatbots.
- Data analysis to detect fraud.

One of the main achievements of the digital economy is the development of electronic payment systems. This not only simplifies trade processes, but also helps to formalize economic activity. Digitalization is transforming traditional processes in the banking system and increasing the speed of services. For example, international payments through mobile banking are being made within minutes.

The McKinsey & Company report indicates that the development directions of both the local and global banking sectors generally coincide. Digital technologies (namely, open APIs, cloud technologies, machine learning, artificial intelligence, robo-advising, etc.), as well as the development of an integrated network economy, will certainly contribute to the transformation of banking customer service models. In the process of developing medium- and long-term strategies, local banks, as well as foreign banks, assess the growth of opportunities for non-banking players to develop the financial market, such as fintech companies, as well as telecommunications and IT companies. In such conditions, large and technologically advanced local banks are implementing strategies for building their ecosystems in order to obtain sources of income that are quite non-traditional for the financial market.

Blockchain technology is serving as an important tool in increasing the security of processes in the banking system. It ensures the transparency of banking operations and reduces the need for intermediaries in payment systems. Along with the development of e-commerce, the banking system is also introducing new payment systems. For example, electronic payments made through mobile applications are growing rapidly in Uzbekistan.

The development of e-commerce is fulfilling the need for digital payment systems. In Uzbekistan, services such as Payme, Click, Apelsin are succeeding in this direction. Cryptocurrencies and digital currencies developed by central banks (CBDC – Central Bank Digital Currency) are shaping a new image of the banking system. Such currencies eliminate intermediaries in international payment systems and allow for faster transactions. Cryptocurrencies and central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) are creating new challenges and opportunities for the banking system. Digital currencies created by central banks can open up new opportunities for national economies.

Digital innovations increase efficiency not only for banks, but also for consumers and small businesses. For example:

- The speed of using banking services has increased.
- Costs have decreased.

The achievements of the digital economy provide a high level of convenience for customers. Banking systems are attracting users with remotely managed services. The issue of cybersecurity remains relevant for the banking system. In the process of digitization, it is necessary to introduce new technologies to protect customer data and combat cyberattacks. Ensuring cybersecurity is one of the key issues in the process of digitization. As a result of the digitization process, traditional jobs in the banking system may decrease, but new, technologically skilled jobs are being created. The digital economy has made it easier to access banking services.

The state is implementing a number of measures to develop the digital economy in Uzbekistan. In particular, by 2030, Uzbekistan aims to increase the share of the digital economy to 30%. In the banking system, the widespread implementation of FinTech projects and the

development of infrastructure in line with international standards are among the priorities. Especially in rural areas, the population now has access to digital services, which is leading to increased financial inclusion.

CONCLUSION

The digital economy and the banking system are inextricably linked, and together they play a significant role in the effective development of the economy. The digitalization process is also being carried out in Uzbekistan at an accelerated pace, and this process is expected to yield significant results in every sector of the economy. Therefore, the issues of developing digital infrastructure and ensuring cybersecurity remain relevant. In the future, further strengthening the integration of the digital economy into the banking system will lead to an improvement in the quality of financial services. In conclusion, the development of the digital economy will increase the efficiency of the banking system and have a positive impact on the economy as a whole. The speed of service provision for customers will increase, and operating costs will decrease. In the modern world, an all-consuming trend towards digitalization is observed in the development of the banking sector of the economy. One of the aspects of this process is the expediency of continuing “live communication” between a bank client and a bank employee, nurtured over decades and even centuries of banking practice.

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